

ABSORPTION CHILLED AUTOMOBILE CLIMATE SYSTEM

Energy distribution in an automobile

Traditional Automobile climate system

Consists of 4 basic elements:

- Evaporator
- Condenser
- Compressor
- Expansion valve

Absorption Chiller based climate system

Consists of only two more components:

- Boiler
- Absorber
- Fluid pump instead of compressor.

Why an absorption chiller?

- Traditional climate system uses up to 10% of cars fuel on a yearly basis.
- Absorption chiller based climate system is “free” - Uses waste heat.
- Reduces automobiles fuel economy with up to 10%
- Thereby reduces CO2 emission with up to 178.000.000 Ton worldwide
- Average Danish car owner saves up to 18.000 kr